

D6.4.7.1 – Kicking off a Data Management Plan (DMP) in an Energy System Research Project

Kicking off a Data Management Plan (DMP) in an Energy System Research Project

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General Information

Summary

Data Management Plans (DMPs) have become increasingly important for open and shared data because they help researchers formalize their intentions for using and sharing their data. However, completing DMPs remains challenging due to the numerous details and large amount of information required. Although websites provide templates to help create DMPs, as offered by the open source tool RDMO¹, there are still many details and questions about storing, maintaining, and using data to be answered while creating a DMP. Typically, one person does not have all the necessary information when preparing a DMP for a large project. To support researchers in creating DMPs, this showcase provides concrete examples of DMPs in various templates, including a description of a typical energy research project. This gives researchers an initial idea of DMPs. To gather the information for completing the DMP, interviews with relevant project participants might be helpful, including data users, data providers, and people responsible for the overall project. Interview questions based on the DMP questions first gather necessary information to create a DMP. Example interview questions are also provided, which have been created for interviews for creating a DMP in a large research project. Thus, the showcase simplifies DMP creation, lowering the barrier to entry and increasing overall DMP use.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

The showcases in [Task Area 6](#) demonstrate how concrete research in the energy domain can profit from the services developed in the other task areas of NFDI4Energy. Thereby, they provide guidance on how to successfully use the service for specific research. The RDMO is part of the NFDI4Energy service portfolio and supports researchers in creating and managing DMPs.

Deliverable (Showcase description)

Internal Documentation

Title: Kicking off a DMP in an energy system research project

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Abstract: Data Management Plans (DMPs) have become increasingly important for open and shared data because they help researchers formalize their intentions for using and sharing their data. However, completing DMPs remains challenging due to the numerous details and large amount of information required. Although websites provide templates to help create DMPs, as offered by

¹ <https://rdmo.aip.de/>, <https://rdmo.nfdi4energy.org/>

RDMO², an open source DMP tool, there are still many details and questions about storing, maintaining, and using data to be answered while creating a DMP. Typically, one person does not have all the necessary information when preparing a DMP for a large project. To support researchers in creating DMPs, this showcase provides concrete examples of DMPs in various templates, including a description of the energy research project. This gives researchers an initial idea of DMPs. To gather the information for completing the DMP, interviews with relevant project participants might be helpful, including data users, data providers and people responsible for the overall project. Interview questions based on the DMP questions first gather necessary information to create a DMP. Example interview questions are also provided, which have been created for interviews for creating a DMP in a large research project. Thus, the showcase simplifies DMP creation, lowering the barrier to entry and increasing overall DMP use.

Link:

- An example DMP in different templates, including a description of the energy research project: <https://cloud.uol.de/s/dXsWFGc48qjenPg>
- The DMPs were created using: <https://rdmo.nfdi4energy.org/>
And: <https://rdmo.aip.de>
- Prioritized interview questions: <https://cloud.uol.de/s/o5SY7qbn7CJXXtr>

NFDI4Energy input: By employing RDMO, NFDI4Energy provides a tool to create and manage DMPs³. Additionally, an example DMP for a specific use case in different templates is made available.

TAs involved: Task Area 1, Task Area 6

Energy research:

In this case, the DMPs consider the topic of self-healing flexibility aggregation, applying distributed artificial intelligence to energy system research. Multiple distributed energy resources are combined into a self-organized, controllable flexibility pool that offers the grid operator aggregated flexibility. A set of interview questions considers energy-sharing communities as an energy research topic.

Meta level: Creating DMPs at the beginning of projects is quite a challenge, as many information and details are required. Tools as RDMO and RDMO4Energy support the creation of DMPs and provide various templates. However, the creation of a DMP remains quite challenging, as na lot of information and details are needed to complete a DMP. By providing a DMP for the same project in the supported DMP templates, NFDI4Energy helps researchers to get an idea of the template structure and its important elements. This supports researchers in creating DMPs.

Enhancement: The example DMPs in different templates were used to determine the interview questions to gather information for creating DMPs for another project. This also supports understanding the structure of a DMP.

Potential testimonials: /

² <https://rdmo.aip.de/>, <https://rdmo.nfdi4energy.org/>

³ <https://rdmo.nfdi4energy.org/>

Lessons learned: Using the service for managing DMPs is a helpful support. Many details are necessary for complete DMPs, the overview and the ability to enter information gradually provided by the service are very helpful.

Brief sections for the website

The Showcase's Starting Point in Energy System Research

The project "Self-Healing Flexibility Aggregation" focuses on applying distributed artificial intelligence to energy system simulation. It combines multiple distributed energy resources into a self-organized, controllable pool of flexibility that offers grid operators aggregated flexibility. Grid operators use this information to perform calculations and determine possible constraint violations. Distributed energy resources considered include battery storage systems, wind devices, and PV plants.

Motivation and Research Requirements

Data Management Plans (DMPs) are an effective way for researchers to communicate their intentions for using, storing and sharing the data from a project. However, at the beginning of a research project like the one in this showcase, not all information about the data to be created is available, so the creation of a DMP can be challenging due to the number of necessary questions and details. Although websites provide templates to help create DMPs, as offered by the open source tool RDMO⁴, there are still many details and questions about storing, maintaining, and using data to be answered while creating a DMP.

NFDI4Energy Solution

By employing RDMO, NFDI4Energy provides a tool (RDMO4Energ) for creating and managing DMPs and thus to support researchers in structuring their research data. To help researchers prepare DMPs, this showcase provides practical examples of DMPs in different templates. This gives researchers an initial idea of what a DMP should look like and what information are needed to complete it.

Interviews with the relevant people, including those using the data in the project, those providing the data, and those responsible for the project as a whole, might be helpful in gathering the information needed to complete the DMP. Example interview questions to gather DMP information are provided as part of the showcase. Thus, the showcase simplifies DMP creation, lowering the barrier to entry and increasing overall DMP use.

⁴ <https://rdmo.aip.de>, <https://rdmo.nfdi4energy.org/>